

Synthesis, antibacterial screening and theoretical molecular properties prediction of hydantoin-chalcone conjugates[†]

Amit Anthwal, Bandana Kumari Thakur and M. S. M. Rawat*

Department of Chemistry, H.N.B. Garhwal University, Srinagar (Garhwal)-246 174, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : msmrawat@gmail.com

Manuscript received 20 December 2013, accepted 20 January 2014

Abstract : Hydantoins and chalcones both are the privileged pharmacophores with significant importance in medicinal chemistry. A series of eleven hydantoin-chalcone conjugates was synthesized and virtually screened for its physicochemical properties. Molinspiration and Osiris software were used for theoretical prediction of physicochemical properties of these molecules. It was found that majority of molecules exhibited theoretical physicochemical properties similar to that of standards. These eleven hybrid compounds were also screened for *in vitro* antimicrobial activity. Few compounds were found active against the pathogenic bacterial strains.

Keywords : Antimicrobial activity, chalcones, hydantoin, Molinspiration, Osiris, pharmacophores.

Introduction

The chalcones and hydantoins are very important pharmacophores, which are present in many biologically active compounds¹⁻⁶. Synthetic analogues of hydantoin are of great interest in chemical industry due to their versatile applications such as anticonvulsants, in epilepsy treatment, as herbicides, fungicides, antimicrobial, virucidal agents, stabilizers in photographic film, and in the preparation of high temperature epoxy resins⁷. Therefore, this pharmacophore is of considerable interest both for medicinal and agrochemical industry⁸. Further, hydantoins derivatives have also been used as a new drugs for treatment of various diseases, for example, nilutamide, which was approved by the FDA in 1996 as a non-steroidal, orally active antiandrogen in the therapy of metastatic prostate cancer^{9,10}. Chalcone derivatives are also reported to exhibit diverse biological activities¹¹⁻¹⁹.

In order to overcome the problem of drug resistance several approaches such as targeting bacterial virulence, genome hunting, high throughput screening (HTS) structure based discovery and combinatorial chemistry have been explored²⁰⁻²². A newer concept in the field of drug discovery is a concept of hybrid molecules, whereby two

pharmacophores are incorporated in a single molecule to exert dual drug action. Due to presence of two pharmacophores hybrid molecule may act on different biological targets which may result in amplification of activity²³. The probability of these hybrid molecules to act on different target may help to overcome problem of drug resistance. We designed hydantoin-chalcone conjugates and anticipated that the new hybrid molecule may have better biological activities. Herein we report synthesis, theoretical molecular properties prediction and *in vitro* anti-microbial screening of 11 new hydantoin-chalcone conjugates.

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

A synthesis of new hybrid molecules involved a multistep protocol. In first step amino group of 1-(4-aminophenyl)ethanone **1a** was chloroacetylated to form *N*-(4-acetylphenyl)-2-chloroacetamide **1b**. The compound **1b** was further refluxed with NaCNO in the presence of tertabutylammonium iodide and ammonium acetate using acetonitrile solvent to yield desired product 3-(4-acetylphenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione **1c**. Further, Claisen-Schmidt condensation reaction of **1c** with substituted al-

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Scheme 1

dehydes resulted in formation of desired hydantoin-chalcone hybrids **1d-1n** in good yield (Scheme 1). New hybrid molecules formed were characterised with help IR, NMR and Mass data.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the hybrid molecules (**1d-1n**) were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities at different concentrations. None of the compound was found active against fungal strains but few compounds were found active against various bacterial strains under study at 500 µg/ml concentration. The results in Table 1 were concluded on the basis of activity at 500 µg/ml concentration. Six hybrid molecules demonstrated moderate to good activity against bacterial strains. The compound **1d** with no substitutions on aromatic ring showed moderate activity

against all the bacterial strains. The compounds with chloro substituents (**1e**, **1g**) were found active against bacterial strains but better results were obtained by chloro substitution at 3-position **1e**. Compound **1j** with bromo substituent at 3-position demonstrated good activity against *S. typhi*, poor activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* but was not active against *K. pneumoniae*. Compound **1l** with fluoro substituent at *para* position was active against all bacterial strains under study but exhibited better activity against *K. pneumoniae*.

Moleinspiration and Osiris study :

Theoretical physicochemical properties and biological activities were calculated using Molinspiration²⁴⁻²⁶ and Osiris software^{24,25,27} for compounds **1d-1n** (Tables 2 and 3). According to Lipinski's rules if drug molecules

Table 1. *In vitro* antibacterial activity at concentration 500 µg/ml

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>S. typhimurium</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>
1f	21	21	18	17	21
1d	10	5	5	8	10
1e	5	5	15	10	8
1g	5	5	10	6	5
1j	6	5	–	12	6
1k	6	5	–	10	6
1l	5	6	10	8	8

Table 2. Molinspiration calculations for compounds **2d-2n**

Comps.	Molecular properties calculations						Drug-likeness properties predictions					
	M.W.	$m_i \log P$	TPSA	OH-NH Interaction	N Violation	Vol.	GPCR	ICM	KI	NRL	PI	EI
2d	306	2.746	66.478	1	0	270.966	0.04	-0.07	-0.17	-0.36	-0.27	-0.25
2e	324	2.910	66.478	1	0	275.897	0.05	-0.08	-0.13	-0.31	-0.27	-0.26
2f	340	3.424	66.478	1	0	248.502	0.04	-0.07	-0.19	-0.36	-0.29	-0.27
2g	396	2.378	94.180	1	0	397.603	-0.03	-0.15	-0.17	-0.38	-0.25	-0.25
2h	351	2.705	112.302	1	0	294.300	-0.10	-0.11	-0.30	-0.40	-0.35	-0.32
2i	340	3.400	66.478	1	0	284.502	0.05	-0.06	-0.20	-0.37	-0.29	-0.27
2j	385	3.532	66.478	1	0	288.851	-0.07	-0.16	-0.25	-0.48	-0.38	-0.33
2k	385	3.556	66.478	1	0	288.851	-0.06	-0.15	-0.21	-0.45	-0.36	-0.31
2l	375	3.851	66.478	1	0	298.037	0.03	-0.09	-0.30	-0.34	-0.30	-0.32
2m	385	3.328	66.478	1	0	288.851	-0.05	-0.23	-0.31	-0.53	-0.39	-0.39
2n	374	3.642	66.478	1	0	302.263	0.09	0.02	-0.09	-0.17	-0.21	-0.21
Zon	212	0.724	86.197	2	0	164.969	-0.40	-0.21	-0.57	-0.28	-0.22	0.28
Cip	331	-0.701	74.569	2	0	285.46	0.12	-0.04	-0.07	-0.19	-0.21	0.28

Zon - Zonisamide (standard anticonvulsant drug), Cip - Ciprofloxacin (antibacterial drug).

GPCRL : GPCR ligand; ICM : Ion channel modulator; KI : Kinase inhibitor; NRL : Nuclear receptor ligand; PI : Protease inhibitor; EI : Enzyme inhibitor.

Table 3. Osiris calculations for compounds **1d-1n**

Comps.	Prediction of toxicity risk				Molecular properties calculations				
	MUT	TUMO	IRRI	REP	M.W.	$c \log P$	$\log S$	D-L	D-S
1d	R	G	G	G	306	2.35	-4.46	1.62	0.41
1e	R	G	G	G	340	2.96	-5.20	4.67	0.38
1f	R	G	G	G	340	2.96	-5.20	5.31	0.38
1g	R	G	G	G	374	3.57	-5.94	5.67	0.32
1h	R	G	G	G	351	2.22	-4.92	-5.59	0.21
1i	R	G	G	G	384	3.05	-5.30	1.27	0.32
1j	R	G	G	G	384	3.05	-5.30	1.46	0.33
1k	R	G	G	G	384	3.05	-5.30	2.68	0.35
1l	R	G	G	Y	324	2.41	-4.78	3.65	0.34
1m	R	G	G	G	374	3.11	-5.24	-2.73	0.19
1n	R	G	G	G	396	2.03	-4.52	7.66	0.42
Zon	G	G	G	R	212	0.41	-3.47	-2.79	0.28
Cip.	R	G	G	Y	331	0.13	-3.32	2.07	0.39

Zon - Zonisamide (standard anticonvulsant drug), Cip - Ciprofloxacin (antibacterial drug), G = No toxicity risk, Y = Low toxicity risk, R = High toxicity risk.

MUT : Mutagenic; TUMO : Tumorigenic; IRRI : Irritant; REP : Reproductive effective. Mol. Wt. : Molecular weight in g/mol; $c \log P$: octanol/water partition coefficient; S : Solubility; DL : Drug likeness; D-S : Drug-score.

have $\log P$ values greater than 5 then there might be a problem for penetration of drug molecule into bio-membrane. We have calculated $\log P$ and TPSA values for compounds **1d-1n** using Molinspiration software and compared them with the values obtained for standard drugs

ciprofloxacin and zonisamide. For all the compounds the calculated $\log P$ values ranges from 2.378 to 3.851 which is good indication. The total polar surface area (TPSA) is calculated from the surface areas that are occupied by oxygen and nitrogen atoms including area occupied by

hydrogen atoms attached to them. Thus, the TPSA is closely related to the hydrogen bonding potential of a compound²⁸. Molecules with TPSA values of 140 Å² or more are expected to exhibit poor intestinal absorption²⁸. It has to be kept in mind that log *P* and TPSA values are only two important factors, although not sufficient, criteria for predicting oral absorption of a molecules under study²⁹. All eleven compounds have TPSA value below 140 Å². Most of compounds are having zero violation of the Rule of 5. Zero violation is good indication, while more than two violations of the Rule of 5 suggest the possibility of problems in bioavailability³⁰. These properties, mainly hydrophobicity, electronic distribution, hydrogen bonding characteristics, molecule size and flexibility, and presence of various pharmacophores are the features that influence the behaviour of molecule in a living organism, including bioavailability, transport properties, affinity to proteins, reactivity, toxicity, metabolic stability and many others. Activity of all compounds and standard drugs were rigorously analysed taking in to account four criteria which are GPCR ligand activity, ion channel modulation, kinase inhibition activity, and nuclear receptor ligand activity. Results of these activities are tabulated in Table 2 by means of numerical assignment. It is very clear from data that all the compounds have negative or very low positive values for these four activities, which is in accordance with values of most of the marketed drugs (GPCR ligand, ion channel modulator, kinase inhibitor, and nuclear receptor ligand)²⁴.

The Osiris calculations are tabulated in Table 3. Toxicity risks (mutagenicity, tumorigenicity, irritation, reproduction) and theoretical physico-chemical properties (solubility, drug likeness and drug score) of compounds **1d-1n** are calculated by the methodology developed by Osiris²⁵. The toxicity risk predictor locates fragments within a molecule which may be responsible for toxicity risk. Toxicity risk alerts are an indication that the drawn structure may be harmful concerning the risk category specified²⁴. From the data presented in Tables 2 and 3 it could be concluded that hybrid molecules have chances of mutagenicity but negligible chances of tumorigenicity, irritation, reproduction effects. All hybrid molecules have log *P* values below 5 which indicates chances of good bioavailability of compounds. Drug likeness may be considered as a complex balance of various structural fea-

tures and molecular properties which predicts similarity of particular molecule with the known drugs compounds. It is clear from Osiris data (Table 3) that all hybrid molecules **1d-1n** have good drug score. As hydantoin is best known for their anticonvulsant activity we have virtually screened zonisamide, an anticonvulsant drug, and compared theoretical properties of hybrid molecules **1d-1n** with the standard anticonvulsant drug. From Molinspiration and Osiris data it could be concluded that if screened for anticonvulsant activity compounds may show encouraging results.

Experimental

General :

The chemicals used in the synthesis were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and were used as such. Thin layer chromatography (Merck TLC silica gel 60 F₂₅₄) was used to monitor the progress of the reaction. The compounds were purified by silica gel column (60–120 mesh). Melting points of the compounds have been measured using automated LABINDIA melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra of synthesized derivatives have been scanned in KBr pellets by using Perkin-Elmer-838 FT-IR spectrophotometer instrument in region from 4000 cm⁻¹ to 667 cm⁻¹. The values have been expressed in ν_{\max} cm⁻¹. Mass spectra were recorded in Waters Micromass LCT Mass spectrometer. The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL ECX spectropin at 400 MHz, using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shift values are recorded on δ scale and the coupling constants (*J*) are in Hz.

Chemistry :

Synthesis of (3-(4-acetylphenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione) (**1c**) :

3.00 mmol of *p*-aminoacetophenone **1a** was dissolved in dichloromethane (DCM) and cooled to 0 °C in ice bath. Further, 9.00 mmol of potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) were added to this reaction mixture followed by dropwise addition of 4.5 mmol of chloroacetyl chloride (ClCOCH₂Cl) at 0 °C temperature. This reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. After completion of reaction, solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure in rotary evaporator. The residue was washed with distilled water to get *N*-(4-acetylphenyl)-2-

chloroacetamide **1b**, which was pure enough to be used in subsequent step. In the next step, 2.00 mmol of **1b** was refluxed with 3.00 mmol of NaCNO in presence of 3.00 mmol of tetra butyl ammonium iodide and ammonium acetate using acetonitrile as solvent at 80 °C for 12 h. After completion of reaction solvent was evaporated. The crude product (3-(4-acetylphenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione) **1c** was extracted with ethyl acetate and was purified with column chromatography using ethyl acetate and hexane as eluent.

General procedure for the synthesis compounds (1d-1n) :

To a well stirred solution of (3-(4-acetylphenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione) **1c** (1.00 mmol) in methanol, 4.00 mmol of LiOH were added followed by the addition of 1.10 mmol of corresponding substituted aldehyde. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. After completion of reaction, precipitate obtained was filtered washed with distilled water. The crude product obtained was purified by recrystallization from methanol.

3-(4-(3-Phenylacryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (1d) : Yield 69% (light yellow solid); m.p. 181 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3364, 2914, 2360, 1659, 1610, 1538, 1497, 1411, 1342, 1314, 1224, 1080, 982, 763; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 3.90 (2H, s), 7.43–7.45 (3H, m), 7.68 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 7.79 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.85–7.88 (2H, m), 7.93 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 8.07 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); TOF MS⁺ m/z 307.1004 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: 306.0097.

3-(4-(3-(3-Chlorophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (1e) : Yield 73% (light yellow); m.p. 230 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3316, 2844, 2363, 1661, 1612, 1540, 1415, 1316, 1225, 1080, 982, 831, 795, 667; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 3.92 (2H, s), 7.44–7.47 (2H, m), 7.65 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 7.80 (3H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.02 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 8.06 (1H, s), 8.11 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); TOF MS⁺ m/z 341.0615 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$: 340.0029.

3-(4-(3-(4-Chlorophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (1f) : Yield 77% (white solid), m.p. 235 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3350, 2933, 2362, 1656, 1613, 1548, 1492, 1410, 1318, 1225, 1097, 981, 820 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 3.93 (2H, s),

7.51 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.67 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 7.82 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.91 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.96 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 8.09 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); TOF MS⁺ m/z 341.0615, Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$: 340.0061.

3-(4-(3-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (1g) : Yield 68% (pale yellow solid); m.p. 253 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3353, 2922, 1697, 1652, 1597, 1532, 1412, 1345, 1233, 1181, 1080, 976, 818, 685 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 4.03 (2H, s), 7.54 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.73 (1H, s), 7.90–7.94 (3H, m), 8.02 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 8.15 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.24 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 Mz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 62.01, 118.93, 125.19, 127.87, 129.43, 129.72, 129.95, 131.45, 132.45, 132.05, 135.45, 136.62, 143.32, 171.65, 187.14; TOF MS⁺ m/z 375.0225 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: 374.0076.

3-(4-(3-(4-Nitrophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (1h) : Yield 74% (yellow solid), m.p. 178 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3353, 2846, 2360, 1659, 1606, 1537, 1415, 1347, 1319, 1223, 1107, 828; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 3.85 (2H, s), 7.73–7.77 (3H, m), 8.08 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.11–8.16 (3H, m), 8.27 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); TOF MS⁺ m/z 351.0855 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$: 350.0064.

3-(4-(3-(2-Bromophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (1i) : Yield 70% (pale yellow); m.p. 211 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3347, 2915, 1697, 1650, 1608, 1536, 1413, 1344, 1233, 1181, 1127, 1079, 1032, 970, 840, 757; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 4.03 (2H, s), 7.38 (1H, t, J 7.3 Hz), 7.47 (1H, t, J 7.3 Hz), 7.73 (1H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 7.91 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 7.96 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 8.14–8.19 (3H, m); TOF MS⁺ m/z 384.0011 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_3$: 383.0006.

3-(4-(3-(3-Bromophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (1j) : Yield 76% (light yellow); m.p. 228 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3362, 2843, 2366, 1660, 1611, 1540, 1412, 1315, 1224, 1083, 981, 831, 792, 666; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz) : δ 3.94 (2H, s), 7.39 (1H, m), 7.61 (1H, d, J 7.3 Hz), 7.64 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 7.81–7.84 (3H, m), 8.02 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 8.11 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.20 (1H, s); TOF MS⁺ m/z 385.0110 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_3$: 384.0001.

3-(4-(3-(4-Bromophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (**1k**): Yield 67% (white solid); m.p. 251 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3355, 2367, 1661, 1612, 1546, 1410, 1337, 1225, 1076, 981, 818, 699; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz): δ 3.86 (2H, s), 7.60–7.64 (3H, m), 7.73 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.82 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.96 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 8.04 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); TOF MS⁺ m/z 385.0110 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_3$: 384.0001.

3-(4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (**1l**): Yield 71% (pale yellow solid); m.p. 202°C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3363, 2845, 2364, 1662, 1599, 1540, 1416, 1321, 1225, 1080, 984, 828, 670; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz): δ 3.93 (2H, s), 7.26–7.30 (2H, m), 7.68 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 7.81 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.90 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 7.92–7.96 (2H, m), 8.08 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); TOF MS⁺ m/z 299.0754 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_3$: 298.0628.

3-(4-(3-(4-(Trifluoromethyl)phenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (**1m**): Yield 73% (yellow solid); m.p. 176 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3321, 1662, 1609, 1537, 1415, 1327, 1223, 1178, 1178, 1124, 1069, 1015, 980, 823, 750, 697; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz): δ 4.01 (2H, s), 7.76 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 7.78–7.81 (2H, m), 7.92 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.07 (1H, d, J 16.1 Hz), 8.07–8.11 (2H, m), 8.16 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 100 MHz): δ 62.05, 118.98, 124.67, 125.65, 129.35, 129.95, 132.19, 138.83, 141.33, 143.28, 171.73, 187.47; TOF MS⁺ m/z 375.0878 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: 374.0798.

3-(4-(3-(3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)imidazolidine-2,4-dione (**1n**): Yield 65% (bright yellow solid); m.p. 201 °C; IR (KBr film, cm^{-1}) ν_{max} : 3311, 2940, 2838, 1690, 1647, 1594, 1503, 1418, 1323, 1282, 1221, 1173, 1122, 1077, 983, 823, 724; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz): δ 3.68 (3H, s), 3.85 (6H, s), 4.03 (2H, s), 7.21 (2H, s), 7.66 (1H, d, J 15.9 Hz), 7.88 (1H, d, J 15.4 Hz), 7.90 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz), 8.15 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz); TOF MS⁺ m/z 397.1321 (M+1), Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$: 396.1276.

Antimicrobial activity:

The antimicrobial bioassay was carried out against five strains of bacteria *Escherichia coli* (MTCC-443), *Salmonella typhimurium* (MTCC-1255), *Klebsiellapneumoniae*

(MTCC-432), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC-737), *Bacillus cereus* (MTCC-430) by the disc diffusion method³¹. Synthesized hybrid molecules (500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were loaded on sterile 4 mm discs. The loaded discs were placed on surface of medium and compound was allowed to diffuse for 5 min. The Muller Hinton agar medium was used to grow the culture of bacterial strains. DMSO was used as solvent as well as control for all compounds. Ciprofloxacin was used as a standard antibacterial drug at 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration.

Conclusion

Novel hydantoin-chalcone conjugates were synthesized; predicted physicochemical properties and screened them for *in vitro* antimicrobial activity. Some compounds were found active against microbial strains under study.

Acknowledgement

AA and BKT are thankful to UGC for research fellowship. MSMR thanks University Grants Commission (F4-10/2010 (BSR) dated 7th March 2012), New Delhi, India for financial support.

Conflict of interest:

The author(s) confirm that this article content has no conflicts of interest.

References

- O. Prakash, A. Kumar, A. Sadana, R. Prakash, P. S. Singh, M. R. Claramunt, D. Sanz, I. Alkorta and J. Elguero, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 6642.
- R. Y. Prasad, L. A. Rao, L. Prasanna, K. Murali and R. P. Kumar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2005, **15**, 5030.
- S. Raghavan and K. Anuradha, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 5181.
- B. A. Bohn, "Introduction to Flavonoids", Harwood Academic, Amsterdam, 1998.
- K. Lavrador, D. Guillerm and G. Guillerm, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 1998, **8**, 1629.
- F. Tellier, F. Acher, I. Brabet, J.-P. Pin and R. Azerad, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **6**, 195.
- C. Syltatk, R. Muller, M. Pietzsch and F. Wagner, "Microbial and enzymatic production of L-amino acids from DL-5-monosubstituted hydantoins", in J. D. Rozell and F. Wagner (eds.), "Biocatalytic Production of Amino Acids and Derivatives", Hanser Publishers, New York, 1992, 131.
- W. B. Yeh, M. J. Lin, M. J. Lee and C. M. Sun, *Mol. Divers.*, 2003, **7**, 185.
- M. Lamothe, M. Lannuzel and M. Perez, *J. Comb. Chem.*,

- 2002, **4**, 73.
10. J. Anderson, *BJU Int.*, 2003, **91**, 455.
 11. Y. B. Vibhute and M. A. Bassar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **42**, 202.
 12. B. A. Bhat, K. L. Dhar, A. K. Saxena and M. Shanmugavel, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **15**, 3177.
 13. L. E. Michael, M. S. David and S. S. Prasad, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1990, **33**, 1948.
 14. R. Kalirajan, M. Palanivelu, V. Rajamanickam, G. Vinothapooshan and K. Andarajagopal, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2007, **5**, 73.
 15. R. H. Udupi, R. Bhat and K. Krishna, *Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1998, **8**, 143.
 16. P. Alka and V. K. Saxena, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, **26**, 390.
 17. G. Urmila, S. Vineeta, K. Vineeta and C. Sanjana, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2005, **14**, 265.
 18. V. K. Pandey, V. D. Gupta and D. N. Tiwari, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2004, **13**, 399.
 19. R. O. Clinton, A. J. Manson, F. W. Stonner, A. L. Beyler, G. O. Potts and A. Arnold, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1513.
 20. Y. M. Lee, F. Almqvist and S. J. Hultgren, *Curr. Opin. Pharmacol.*, 2003, **3**, 513.
 21. R. Bax, N. Mullan and J. Verhoef, *Int. J. Antimicrob. Agents*, 2000, **16**, 51.
 22. I. Chopra, J. Hodgson, B. Metcalf and G. Poste, *J.A.M.A.*, 1996, **275**, 401.
 23. D. Schellenbrg, S. Abdulla and C. Roper, *Curr. Mol. Med.*, 2006, **6**, 253.
 24. A. Parvez, J. Meshram, V. Tiwari, J. Sheik, R. Dongre, M. H. Youssoufi and T. B. Hadda, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 4370.
 25. A. Parvez, J. Meshram and T. B. Hadda, *Phosphorus, Sulphur Silicon Relat. Elem.*, 2010, **185**, 1.
 26. www.molinspiration.com.
 27. www.osiris.com.
 28. V. N. Viswanadhan, A. K. Ghose, G. R. Revankar and R. K. Robins, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1989, **29**, 163.
 29. V. N. Viswanadhan, A. K. Ghose, G. R. Revankar and R. K. Robins, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1989, **29**, 163.
 30. C. A. Lipinski, F. Lombardo, B. W. Dominy and P. J. Feeney, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.*, 2001, **46**, 3.
 31. R. Verpoorte, T. van Beek, A. Thomassen, P. Andeweil, J. Baerhim and A. Svendsen, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 1983, **8**, 287.

